

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
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IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF THE EFFICIENCY OF FINANCIAL ACTIVITY OF AGRICULTURAL AGROCLUSTERS OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: In this article, the econometric analysis of the factors affecting the financial activity of the existing agricultural agroclusters in Uzbekistan and their assessment are made, and scientific recommendations on forecast indicators are developed. Since the research data are based on multivariate time series, the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model was used to develop the econometric models.

Key words: agrocluster analysis, agrocluster financing, economic analysis, cotton-textile clusters, economic efficiency, econometric analysis, forecast indicators.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistondagi mavjud qishloq xo'jaligi agroklastlarining moliyaviy faoliyatiga ta'sir etuvchi omillar ekonometrik tahlil qilingan va ularga baho berilgan, prognoz ko'rsatkichlari bo'yicha ilmiy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan. Tadqiqot bo'yicha ma'lumotlar ko'p o'zgaruvchili vaqtli qatorlarga asoslanganligi uchun ekonometrik modellarni ishlab chiqishda avtoregressiv taqsimlangan kechikish (ARDL) modeli qo'llanildi.

Kalit so'zlar: agroklastlar tahlili, agroklastlarni moliyalashtirish, iqtisodiy tahlil, paxta-to'qimachilik klasterlari, iqtisodiy samaradorlik, ekonometrik tahlil, prognoz ko'rsatkichlari.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассмотрен эконометрический анализ факторов, влияющих на финансовую деятельность существующих сельскохозяйственных агрокластеров Узбекистана, их оценка, а также разработаны научные рекомендации по прогнозным показателям. Поскольку данные исследования основаны на многомерных временных рядах, для разработки эконометрических моделей использовалась модель авторегрессии с распределенным лагом (ARDL).

Ключевые слова: агрокластерный анализ, финансирование агрокластеров, экономический анализ, хлопково-текстильные кластеры, экономическая эффективность, эконометрический анализ, прогнозные показатели.

INTRODUCTION

Foreign experience shows that agroclusters as a changing ecosystem play a decisive role in stimulating agricultural growth, supporting innovation and facilitating the production of agricultural products. Agricultural agroclusters encourage adoption of innovative technologies and serve to reduce costs and implement smart specialization strategies ^[2].

However, in our country, the econometric analysis of the organizational-economic and financial efficiency of agricultural agroclusters, the identification of factors affecting efficiency and the creation of forecast indicators have not been carried out sufficiently.

Clustering of small agricultural enterprises in agro-industrial clusters allows to expand production possibilities, increase competitiveness and access to new markets. Agroclusters are a transitional form of agricultural ecosystems and are classified according to various criteria ^[3].

Effective functioning of clusters in agriculture leads to economic growth and increases the competitiveness of the regional economy ^[4]. Also, agroclusters have been found to have a positive effect on farmers' innovation propensity through cognitive capital, social belonging, and perceived competence ^[5].

Agrocluster brings together different stakeholders in agriculture, from farmers and processors to researchers and practitioners. Financial analysis serves as an approach that guides agroclusters to sustainable development, efficient allocation of resources, and strategic decision-making.

Financial analysis of agroclusters includes an assessment of the financial performance and viability of individual enterprises and the cluster as a whole. Such an analysis includes an assessment of the financial status of enterprises, their financial efficiency, stability and profitability ^[6]. Various financial indicators are used to calculate various components of financial condition, such as solvency, liquidity and financial stability ratios. Evaluation of agroclusters is carried out using the methods of financial statement analysis and comparative analysis of financial analysis ^[7].

Improving the financial analysis of agroclusters is very important for identifying financial problems, establishing causal relationships and finding ways to improve the financial situation ^[8]. Development of a system for assessing the financial condition of agroclusters, which allows to determine the probability of a financial crisis by using multi-factor indicator models ^[9]. Also, special liquidity indicators can be used to analyze the liquidity of assets in agroclusters, which is an important financial tool for assessing solvency ^[10].

The results of the analysis are used in making management decisions, evaluating public policy and developing recommendations for improving agriculture. It includes a variety of tools and techniques, including ratio analysis, cash flow analysis, and financial modeling. These analyzes provide valuable information on the profitability, liquidity, solvency and efficiency of agrocluster entities, enabling stakeholders to make informed decisions.

Therefore, in this study, an econometric analysis of the factors affecting the financial activity of the existing agricultural agroclusters in Uzbekistan and their assessment were made, and scientific recommendations were developed on forecast indicators.

LITERARY ANALYSIS

Many foreign scientists have conducted research on improving the financial analysis of agroclusters. In particular, M. Beranova and others conducted primary research on a statistical sample of agricultural agroclusters and found that state subsidies play an important role in the financial performance of organizations in this field. Their research findings show that agroclusters focus on key drivers of financial performance, including operating profit, capital structure, and cost of capital ^[11].

Sergey Butorin emphasized the importance of agroclusters as a promising form of association for business entities that enables innovative development through cooperation and strategic partnership. In his opinion, effective mechanisms of transformation of production capacity and re-production of technical potential of agrocluster economic entities will lead to development. Integration and cooperation of production and sales in agroclusters serves to commercialize production, technological and innovative areas, making them more convenient for consumers ^[12].

Also, many econometric models have been developed by foreign scientists on the factors influencing the financial activity of agroclusters. In particular, Putsenteilo P. and others developed a method of calculating economic and financial indicators based on the interdependence of partner enterprises of agro-industrial clusters. The results of the econometric research of the scientists show that attracting investments to the agrocluster will lead to a decrease in the production of agricultural products in the country if the negative forecast is maintained at the average level of the previous ears. If investment attraction increases by 20%, (realistic forecast) production will increase by 1.86%. Comparing the forecasted volumes of agricultural production with domestic needs will help to estimate the volume of exports of products in the future ^[13].

R. Litvin developed econometric models for forecasting economic indicators of agricultural enterprises and agroclusters with direct foreign investment. In the study, practical econometric methods were used to forecast the economic indicators of agroclusters in 2000–2011. The scientist developed linear trend, parabolic trend and exponential trend models for the research and explained that the experimental data from 2000 to 2009 are adequate. According to the coefficients of the regression equations, cash flow, asset value and sales revenue had a positive effect on the net profit of the agrocluster ^[14].

Serhii Lehenchuk et al used panel data regression analysis to study the relationship between financial performance indicators of agroclusters and various independent variables. The study used factors such as leverage, materiality of assets, debt-to-equity ratio, current ratio, capital density, size, and legal form and type of ownership as factors that significantly affect the financial performance of agroclusters in different countries. According to the results of the study. factors such as current ratio, debt equity and capital intensity have a significant impact on financial performance indicators in agroclusters ^[15].

Among foreign scientists, Jr. Tabe-Ojong and others emphasized the importance of taking into account the specific economic characteristics and environment of agroclusters in the analysis of factors determining financial results. According to the econometric equations of the study, agroclusters have been shown to have a positive relationship in reducing household income and per capita income, poverty and disparities in poverty. Also, according to the results of the regression equations, agroclusters are associated with an increase in welfare for all households and lead to a significant increase in agricultural income and welfare [16].

Among the European scientists, Lehenchuk and others developed regression equations based on panel data of the determinants of financial performance of agroclusters in their research. The study found a negative effect of the number of Slovakian agroclusters on return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE). It is also found that debt to equity has a positive effect on ROE. According to the results of the study, there is a direct relationship between financial indicators in the Slovak agricultural sector, which can be used to improve management decisions, evaluate agricultural sector decisions and make recommendations for improving the sector [17].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Since the data in this study are based on multivariable time series, the autoregressive allocated lag ARDL (Autoregressive allotted lag) model was used in the development of econometric models. The ARDL model is widely used in econometric methods due to its flexibility and the ability to analyze long-term relationships between variables.

This model includes autoregressive distributed lag terms, this model is widely used in modeling various economic processes [18].

The ARDL model is used in cointegration analysis because it allows testing and analyzing the degree of relationship between variables. The ARDL model was used to study the dynamic causal relationships between macroeconomic indicators such as inflation rate, exchange rate, money supply and GDP in different countries [19]. Also, the ARDL model has been used to study the causal relationship between spot, futures and options markets and the relationship between prices in financial markets [20].

The ARDL model is described in detail in the scientific paper "boundary testing approaches for the analysis of long-run relationships" by the famous economists Pesaran, Shin, and Smith, and is widely used in economic, environmental, and political science programs [21].

The ARDL model has been used in poverty reduction research in Kenya, where economic growth has been found to contribute to poverty reduction [22]. It was also used to study the relationship between savings, investment and economic growth in Ethiopia, which found that savings and investment are related to real GDP [23].

The ARDL model provided evidence for long-run relationships between productivity, unemployment, tax payments, union strength and wages in a study of the UK earnings equation [24].

Integration is a procedure used to make non-stationary time series stationary. The ARDL model allows variables to be combined with order 0, order 1, or a combination of both [25].

The ARDL model is known for its flexibility in dealing with stationary and non-stationary variables. It includes autoregressive (AR) and distributed lag (DL) terms, which enable the analysis of dynamic relationships in time series data. The model is used to examine the long-term and short-term effects of the variables, as well as to examine cointegration and the existence of long-run relationships between the variables of interest. This versatility is especially important when processing economic and financial time series data that describe non-stationary variables [26].

In our previous research work, we developed a number of scientific recommendations on improving the methodology of financial efficiency analysis of agroclusters [27-34]. Our work is their logical continuation.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

According to the research, the statistical agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan (www.stat.uz) and the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan (www.agro.uz) from 2001 to 2022, in connection with the development of the financial activity of agricultural organizations and agroclusters in our republic and their impact on it, in total Economic indicators of 22 observations were used as data sources.

The fit of the regression equation derived from the ARDL model was assessed by Gaussian Markov significance criteria and Cusum diagnostic test scores. According to the econometric model, the delayed effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable in subsequent ears was estimated. Agricultural and agrocluster output (dependent variable) is affected by factors such as the amount of investment in agricultural agroclusters, the land area of agricultural agroclusters, and the number of agricultural agroclusters.

At the next stage of the research, the analytical graphic representation of dependent and independent variables over time was expressed (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Analytical graphical representation of dependent and independent variables over time¹

It can be seen from Figure 1 that the factors of agricultural agrocluster products and investment volume factors in agricultural agroclusters have shown an upward trend in previous ears and forecast ears. Land areas of agricultural agroclusters showed a state of stationarity in the analyzed period of time, and the number of agricultural agroclusters showed trend lines of decline in the analyzed period of time.

Figure 2: Standardized normal probability plot of dependent and independent variables²

1 Independently developed by the author
 2 Independently developed by the author

Figure 2 illustrates the use of parametric statistical analysis involving dependent and independent variables. This approach serves to increase the reliability and interpretability of subsequent analyses. In addition, the standardized normal probability plot for the dependent variable shows the approximate probability of the data points with a diagonal line. The fact that the independent variables consistently followed a diagonal pattern across all plots strengthened confidence in the assumption of normality. Also, the decrease in the number of agricultural agroclusters over the ears and the state of change indicate that certain balances in this distribution have been disturbed.

At the next stage of the research, the correlation matrix was checked for each of the dependent and independent variables based on the Stata program (Table 1).

Table 1: Correlation matrix of dependent and independent variables³

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
(1) Agricul_prod	1.000			
(2) investment	0.6994	1.000		
	(0.0000)			***
(3) Agricul_ac~g	-0.5432	-0.6226	1.000	
	(0.0000)	(0.0015)		***
(4) agricul_or~n	-0.6883	-0.6893	0.4243	1.000
	(0.0000)	(0.0000)	(0.0436)	***

The relationship between the dependent and independent variables showed that there is a high, strong and inverse correlation between the dependent variable and the factors influencing it. Also, the correlation matrix presented in Table 1 showed that there is no multicollinearity between the dependent variable (outcome) and independent variables (characteristic factors), and considering that the p value is less than 0.05, it indicates the strength of the reliability of the correlation relationship.

In the next step, the Unit-root test was conducted to determine the stationarity of the dependent and independent variables (Table 2).

Table 2: Unit-root test scores on dependent and independent variables⁴

O'zgaruvchilar	Test Statistic	1% Critical Value	5% Critical Value	10% Critical Value	p-value for Z(t)
Bog'liq o'zgaruvchi (Agricul_prod)	-4.579	-3.750	-3.000	-2.630	0.0062
Mustaqil o'zgaruvchi (investment)	-3.848	-3.750	-3.000	-2.630	0.0025
Mustaqil o'zgaruvchi (Agricul_ac~g)	-6.060	-3.750	-3.000	-2.630	0.0000
Mustaqil o'zgaruvchi (agricul_or~n)	-4.096	-3.750	-3.000	-2.630	0.0010

Based on the data presented in Table 2 above, the unit-root test (Unit-root) obtained a statistical value of (-4.579) for the dependent variable and values of (-3.848, -6.060 and -4.096) for the independent variables. The results of the unit-root test show that the dependent and independent variables have reached stationarity, which is confirmed by the minimum McKinnon values of $Z(t) = 0.0062, 0.0025, 0.0000$ and 0.0010 .

An econometric model was developed using the ARDL model for the study. Below is an econometric model based on the ARDL model.

$$\Delta \text{Agricul_prod}_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \sum_{p=1}^n \Delta y_{i,t-p} + \alpha_2 \sum_{p=1}^n \Delta \text{investment}_{1i,t-p} + \alpha_3 \sum_{p=1}^n \Delta \text{Agric_acreg}_{2i,t-p} + \alpha_4 \sum_{p=1}^n \Delta \text{Agricul_organ}_{3i,t-p} + \gamma_1 Y_{i,t-p} + \gamma_2 X_{1i,t-1} + \gamma_3 X_{2i,t-1} + \gamma_4 X_{3i,t-1} + \epsilon_{i,t} \quad (1)$$

Equation (1) represents the linear ARDL model, y gives short- and long-term forecasts. Also, in the next step, the ARDL model econometric equation was developed in the following table based on the Stata program (Table 3).

³ It was developed independently by the author based on the Stata program

⁴ It was developed independently by the author based on the Stata program

Table 3: ARDL(2,2,2,0) model regression equation indicators⁵

ARDL(2,2,2,0)	regression
Sample: 2003–2023	Number of obs = 21
R-squared = 0.7030	Root MSE = 0.1117
Adj R-squared = 0.6600	Log likelihood = 23.017594

D.						
Agricul_prod	Coef.	Std.Err.	t	P>t	[95%Conf.	Interval]
ADJ						
Agricul_prod						
L1.	-0.832	0.186	-4.480	0.001	-1.241	-0.423
LR						
investment	1.095	0.051	21.430	0.000	0.982	1.207
Agricul_acreg	8.686	1.523	5.700	0.000	5.333	12.039
agricul_organ	0.165	0.116	1.430	0.081	-0.090	0.420
SR						
Agricul_prod						
LD.	0.479	0.194	2.470	0.031	0.051	0.907
investment						
D1.	-0.201	0.263	-0.760	0.461	-0.778	0.377
LD.	-0.461	0.250	-1.850	0.092	-1.011	0.089
Agricul_acreg						
D1.	-4.439	1.567	-2.830	0.016	-7.888	-0.990
LD.	-3.925	1.218	-3.220	0.008	-6.606	-1.245
_cons	-60.168	16.439	-3.660	0.004	-96.349	-23.987

The R-squared value in the ARDL (2,2,2,0) model is 0.70, indicating that approximately 70% of the variation in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variables included in the model. Also, the specified combination of lagged dependent and independent variables, other factors taken into account in the model together help to explain a significant part of the observed changes in the dependent variable. This indicates the moderately strong level of explanatory power for a given model specification.

The Log likelihood probability value 23.017594 in the ARDL (2,2,2,0) model represents the maximum value of the logarithm of the likelihood function given the observed data. In statistical modeling, Log likelihood is an important measure used to evaluate the fit of the model to the data.

The Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) value of 0.1117 in the ARDL (2,2,2,0) model represents the root mean square of the squared differences between the observed values and the predicted values of the dependent variable. Basically, it provides an estimate of the average magnitude of the model’s residuals or forecast errors. In this context, a Root MSE of 0.1117 indicates that the model’s predictions deviate by about 0.1117 units from the observed values. From the point of view of this regression analysis, the positive econometric result indicates that the ARDL model with fixed parameters can effectively explain the fluctuations in the dependent variable.

High R-squared values, favorable Log likelihood results, and reduced RMSE together indicate a robust fit of the model to the data, giving it the ability to capture important aspects of underlying economic dynamics.

CONCLUSIONS AND OFFERS

The following proposals and recommendations were developed as a result of the analysis and conclusions of the study of the interaction of the products of agricultural agroclusters in the national economy, the volume of investment in agricultural agroclusters, the land areas of agricultural agroclusters and the number of agricultural agroclusters.

⁵ Developed by the author

According to the ARDL (2,2,2,0) model,

1. A 1% increase in the volume of investments in agricultural agroclusters leads to an increase in the output of agricultural agroclusters by 1.09%. This indicates that there is little more than a positive and proportional relationship between investment volume and output. This means that more investment in these sectors will lead to higher output.
2. A 1% increase in the land area of agricultural agroclusters leads to an 8.68% increase in the products of agricultural agroclusters. This shows an important and serious relationship between land area and production. Also, the expansion of land areas intended for agricultural agrocluster activities leads to a significant increase in production, which reflects the importance of land resources in these sectors.
3. A 1% increase in the number of agroclusters in agriculture leads to a 0.16% increase in agricultural agrocluster products. This indicates a significant correlation between the number of organizations and output. This means that the increase in the number of agricultural agroclusters contributes positively to the growth of production, represents a positive effect on other factors such as investments and land area.
4. These econometric results emphasize the importance of investments, land area and the number of organizations in the production of agricultural agrocluster products in the national economy. They provide insight into the key factors affecting production levels in these sectors and provide researchers, practitioners and stakeholders with an important input into decision-making processes related to agricultural development and investment.

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